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ATTACKING DIMENSIONAL INSTABILITY PROBLEMS
IN GRAPHITE/EPOXY STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The sources of dimensional instability in graphite/epoxy structures are numerous and can be both micro or macro in nature. They can be related to environmental changes, part geometry, laminate orientation, microcracking, and other factors.

Past and current experiences in working with graphite/epoxy to fabricate dimensionally stable instrument structures at Composite Optics, Incorporated, has given rise to new understanding and techniques for achieving higher degrees of dimensional stability.

This paper describes these sources of dimensional instability, provides alternatives for minimizing or eliminating them, and presents test data illustrating the effectiveness of these techniques used to dimensionally stabilize a graphite/epoxy structure.

KEYWORDS: Graphite/Epoxy; Composite; Dimensional Stability; Instrument Design; CTE/CME.

1. INTRODUCTION

The scientific exploration of the earth and the universe, our journeys to distant planets, and our global communication networks require designs and materials capable of extreme dimensional stability over a wide range of environmental conditions.

With the cost-per-pound of payload boosted into orbit increasing every year and the added challenge of maintaining exact dimensional stability, the usage of composites for space structures is becoming of paramount importance. Material development and application have developed substantially over the last twenty years and we are now able to produce lightweight composite structures with near-zero coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE's) which are dimensionally stable in ambient or space environments.

Obtaining this dimensional stability has required many years of development and experimentation. Material characteristics as well as design and manufacturing practices contribute to a dimensionally stable system. Instabilities may occur as a result of macro and micro distortion within the

composite. This paper summarizes the various design, manufacturing, and material approaches which have been applied to maximize dimensional stability in space structures.

2. DISCUSSION

2.1 Sources of Macro Dimensional Instability Macro distortions in structures can be defined as distortions on the order of thousandths of an inch. Some sources of macro dimensional instability are:

- Springback of laminated angles and other formed shapes
- Cut-outs in cylinders
- Bowing of flat panels and ovalizing of cylinders
- Tooling-induced distortion

2.1.1 Springback Springback occurs when composite laminates are formed into angles during processing. Springback or angle closure occurs to the extent of about 1½ degrees (Reference 1) upon removal of the laminate from the tool. Exposure to ambient conditions will open this angle (via moisture absorption) to return to, or even exceed, the original angle. Through-the-thickness expansion of the laminate is the source of this dimensional instability.

Structures can be very sensitive to this problem as was discovered over ten (10) years ago in testing of the GEMS Forward Mirror Support (Reference 2). This problem has often been overlooked by designers over the years and needs to be considered whenever composites are utilized on dimensionally stable structures.

2.1.2 Cut-outs in Cylinders Some design approaches require holes in the sides of cylinders. The degree of initial distortion when the holes are formed is surprisingly large and the stresses generated can force the cylinders out of round and the ends out of true flatness and/or parallelism. Through-the-thickness expansion of the laminate is again the source of this dimensional instability.

2.1.3 Bowing, Warping, Ovalization When laying up a flat panel or a cylinder, the typical fiber angle tolerance from the true angle is $\pm 2^\circ$. This manufacturing tolerance is a major contributor to the bowing or warping of a panel. The thicker the laminate, the more susceptible it is to these variations, in that substantial forces are required to compensate for the bowing or warping. The laminates can straighten upon moisture absorption, and drying the laminate to its original state will bring back the original cured laminate geometry.

2.1.4 Tooling Effects Tool size can have a detrimental effect on laminate distortions if the pressure applied during cure is retained during cool down. For large flat parts, small wrinkles can develop in the laminate. Cylinders can also wrinkle and even buckle as the tool shrinks away. High expansion of a tool can induce resin gradients which can lead to macro instabilities in the laminate.

2.2 Sources of Micro Dimensional Instability Micro distortions in laminates occur in the order of millionths of an inch for a dimensionally stable structure.

Some sources of micro dimensional instability are:

- Through-the-thickness expansion of the laminate
- Coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch at interfaces between parts
- CTE variations in laminates
- Response to moisture (coefficient of moisture expansion -- CME)
- Microcracking

2.2.1 Micro Through-the-Thickness Expansion The through-the-thickness CTE of a laminate approaches the magnitude of the matrix resin (15 ppm/°F to 20 ppm/°F). The resulting instability problems range from micro to macro effects. An example of this is the Telescope Metering Structure (TMS) Spider design (Reference 3). A thick spider arm slips into slots in the end of a telescope cylinder. With the ends of slots left open, the spider's through-the-thickness expansion would expand against the slot in the cylinder, forcing an opening of the slot which forces the cylinder to flare outwardly at the end. This causes the spider arm to tilt up. Here, the effective CTE of the TMS was 0.80 ppm/°F when the slot was allowed to open and 0.02 ppm/°F when the slot was held closed. To alleviate this instability, the slot was held closed by a cap that prevented the through-the-thickness expansion of the spider from opening the cylinder slots.

2.2.2 Through-the-Thickness Expansion Since through-the-thickness expansion in an optical path has up to 1000 times the expansion effect as the basic in-plane expansion of the laminate, severe distortions can result if the design does not compensate for this effect. An egg-crate core of an optical bench (which may have a CTE of 0.02 ppm/°F and a through-the-thickness CTE of 20 ppm/°F) was slotted on only one side of the support core (Figure 1). The bench bowed during temperature cycling and moisture changes caused very severe bowing due to the core asymmetry.

2.2.3 CTE Variation Within a Laminate or Laminate-to-Laminate The CTE within a laminate can also vary and be a source of dimensional instability. These CTE variations may be as much as 25%. Table 1 represents data collected from the Hubble Telescope Fine Guidance System Keel work-in-process (WIP) coupon (Reference 4). Note the 30% difference in the average CTE for the 0° and 90° directions. Also, the CTE of some specimens are twice the average CTE from laminate-to-laminate for this same lot of material.

If a large laminate is cut up in the same or different directions to make parts and they are assumed to have the same CTE, dimensional instability could occur. CTE mismatches can cause a mirror to tilt in the main body of a telescope or an optical bench to bend if opposite surfaces are composed of materials' having different CTE's.

FIGURE 1. TYPICAL EGG-CRATE RIB IN AN OPTICAL BENCH
CORRECT AND INCORRECT SLOTSING METHOD

TABLE 1. WIP TEST COUPONS FOR P75S/930 FGS-KEEL

<u>LAMINATE NO.</u>	<u>CTE 0° PPM/°F</u>	<u>CTE 90° PPM/°F</u>
1	0.09	0.10
2	0.04	0.09
3	0.10	0.02
4	0.05	0.04
5	0.11	0.03
6	-.02	-0.05
AVERAGE CTE	.06	.04

2.2.4 Response to Moisture

The effects of moisture are well known and characterized for some dimensionally stable composite structures (References 5 and 6). The effect of moisture on a laminate can be many times greater than the effect of a wide temperature change for a space structure. A thermally stable structure 100 inches long with a CTE of 0.02 ppm/°F and which experiences a temperature change of 100°F will distort 0.0002 inches. That same structure's response to moisture is 80 ppm in an R.H. of 53% over 40 days (typical for graphite/epoxy), causing a distortion of 0.008 inches which is 40 times that of the maximum temperature change. The Mars Observer Camera is an example of this situation. The camera's sensitivity to moisture is such that in less than an hour it can exceed focus requirements at 50% R.H., whereas temperature variation of over a 100°F poses no dimensional or focus problem.

2.2.5 Microcracking Microcracking of a composite causes the following dimensional stability problems:

- Produces a hysteresis effect in the structure
- Changes the CTE (the CTE becomes more negative with increased thermal cycling)
- Moisture response rates increase

Figure 2 illustrates the effect of composite microcracking. As the temperature is lowered and reaches the threshold of microcracking (as evidenced by an abrupt strain change), the curve changes to a new slope.

Microcracking is occasionally employed to achieve a desired CTE. The Hubble Telescope Metering Structure (Reference 7) illustrates the point at which microcracking was recognized and thereby used to "tune" the various struts to a desired CTE.

FIGURE 2. INTERPRETATION OF COMMON EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE MEASUREMENTS ILLUSTRATING MICROCRACKING OF PSEUDOISOTROPIC GY-70/930 (0°/45°/90°/135°)_s .12mm/PLY

2.3 Structural Design Considerations The challenge in effectively employing composite laminates for dimensionally stable applications is to recognize and control the various sources of micro and macro dimensional instability through material selection, design approaches (details and assembly), and manufacturing techniques.

2.3.1 Material Selection Material selection is often the key to the design of dimensionally stable parts. Dynamic and thermal stability requirements dictate the type of fiber (Table 2) required, but there can be some latitude in fiber modulus selection since laminate thicknesses can be adjusted to offset changes in modulus. Temperature requirements affect the selection of the matrix material. For purposes of this discussion, no high-temperature matrix systems (e.g., thermoplastics) are considered.

TABLE 2. WIDE RANGE OF MATERIAL CTEs AVAILABLE

<u>Fiber Modulus</u>	<u>Pseudoisotropic CTE (PPM/°F)</u>
32 MSI	1.5 to 2.0
55 MSI	.30 to .40
75 MSI	± 0.1
100 MSI	-0.4 to -0.6

The following procedure can be used for the selection of an appropriate fiber and resin system to minimize microcracking and moisture response.

- Establish the thermal range of the exposure environment (Figure 2).
- Determine the stiffness, CTE, and weight requirements of the application.
- Use a thinner cure ply thickness prepreg if the higher modulus materials are required to minimize microcracking.
- Select a resin system compatible with the thermal and mechanical requirements (Reference 8).
- Determine if moisture barrier protection is required (Reference 9).
- Establish the optimal fiber orientation (References 8 and 10).
- Determine a detail system design approach.
- Ensure adequate in-process testing to confirm needed properties of detail parts.
- Test end item to verify if design criteria have been met.

2.3.2 Moisture Protection A number of ways to prevent, or compensate for, moisture-induced dimensional instability have appeared previously in the literature (Reference 9). The methods include:

- Use of adjustable optics
- Instrumentation preset to compensate for hygrostrain
- Use of a "bakeout" procedure and controlled environment
- Employment of a moisture barrier
- Combinations of the above methods

The moisture barrier approach has been utilized on many structures because the other options were not always feasible or cost effective.

Recent work on various new hydrophobic resin systems has offered designers an alternative solution to the hygrostrain problem. Modified epoxy resins and cyanate-ester resins can reduce the hygrostrain to acceptable levels for dimensionally stable structures. Research at Lockheed Missiles and Space Company (LMSC) (Reference 11) which evaluated several modified epoxy resin systems indicated that 3M's PR-500 (P75S) exhibited a hygrostrain of approximately 45 ppm after one year at 100% RH exposure, while typical epoxies yielded 150 ppm hygrostrain after the same period. COI has been evaluating several of these new systems and the results are extremely encouraging.

The test data presented in Figure 3 illustrate how significant Fiberite's 954-3 resin can be to minimize the hygrostrain of this composite. It should be noted that a complete characterization of these new systems is in progress and no structure has been fully space-qualified using the new materials. Moisture will still absorb and desorb from the new modified epoxies and cyanate-esters, even though their strain

FIGURE 3. HYGROTHERMAL STRAIN CHANGES IN P75S/954-3 COMPOSITES SATURATED AT VARIOUS RELATIVE HUMIDITIES

responses are significantly reduced. A barrier can reduce the rates of strain change to an imperceptible level. Moisture barriers are still appropriate and effective in preventing moisture absorption and desorption for this reason. Some optical structures can be contaminated by outgassed material condensing on critical surfaces and, therefore, must be sealed to prevent this contamination from occurring.

Test results for P75S/ERL1962 shown in Figures 4 and 5 demonstrate the reduced quantity of water diffusing from a sealed system. These test results were performed on a truss structure, Figure 6, that represents the next generation light-weight instrument structures planned by NASA. COI is currently performing these tests for NASA/GSFC.

FIGURE 4. LONG-TERM MOISTURE ABSORPTION STRAIN EFFECTS ON NASA TRUSS STRUCTURE

FIGURE 5. LONG-TERM MOISTURE DESORPTION STRAIN EFFECTS ON NASA TRUSS STRUCTURE

FIGURE 6. NASA TRUSS DETAILS FOR MOISTURE ABSORPTION AND DESORPTION TESTING

2.4 Design Approach Both macro and micro dimensional instability sources must be regarded in the design of a structure. Basic design philosophies can be challenged in attempting to eliminate sources of macro dimensional instability because of the influence of traditional aerospace structure design configurations. Conventional stiffeners and rings for semi-monocoque structures are usually "HAT", "Z", or "C" shaped, and, of course, fasteners are used to attach the detail parts together. These detail shapes would be formed by bending fibers around an angle which is not a desirable practice.

The simplest, most predictable and dimensionally stable composite structure is a flat plate laminate when properly manufactured. The next most stable structure would be assemblies of flat plate details to form a bonded assembly. Surfaces of revolution, provided they are uninterrupted by slots or holes, are also very stable (i.e., cylinders, cones or spheres).

To retain high dimensional stability, the best joining approach for composite structures is bonded joints. It has been shown that bonded joints of flat elements (edge bonds to flat panel) are structurally adequate. Joining techniques, such as mortise and tenon, dado, corner blocks and very thin clips, have been employed with great success (Reference 4). The use of these joints has

increased in recent years because of the concomitant increase in interlaminar strength of the modified epoxy matrix resins used in these structures.

The relatively new fiber/resin combination of T50/ERL1962 has been shown to have twice the flatwise tension strength of "standard" systems (P75/934 or P75/930) which is critical in the design of bonded joints. The ERL1962 resin system has been extensively employed in dimensionally stable hardware such as the Mars Observer Camera, the Starlab Infrared Camera (IRCA), the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite High Resolution Doppler Imager (UARS-HRDI) Bench, and the Advanced Communications Technology Satellite (ACTS) Reflector System. These space structures also employ minimal mechanical fastener design approaches.

Design symmetry is also extremely important for telescope and optical bench structures. The cross-section of a secondary mirror support where a spider arm intersects the main cylinder and ring of a telescope needs to be completely symmetrical at the top and bottom surfaces to prevent induced thermal/moisture strains.

Optical bench structure cross-sections are also designed symmetrically through their thickness. When metal details are used on a top surface for mounting equipment, the bottom surface often has a compensating metal plate to counter the differences in CTE produced by the fittings.

The importance of uniform laminate thickness across an assembly must also be considered because of the hygrostrain response difference over time. The use of hydrophobic resins and/or moisture barriers eliminates this problem.

2.5 Manufacturing Techniques A major advancement in manufacturing techniques for attacking planar laminate instability has recently been developed. A "rotate and fold" laminate technique (Reference 12) was developed at Sandia Laboratories to produce an isotropic laminate with major axes stiffnesses within 5% of each other. The tensile moduli, CTE, and strength values in the 0° and 90° directions have been verified by testing. This technique is depicted in Figure 7 (taken from Reference 12). In essence, ply lay-up tolerances are canceled out by becoming symmetric with the resulting laminate properties truly isotropic throughout the laminate.

COI has been using the "folded" approach on critical structures for some time with considerable success, but not until this work was initiated by Mr. C. Martin Hinckley at Sandia were the resulting benefits completely understood and improved upon.

The test results in Table 3, which are for a "folded" laminate only, exemplify the degree of uniformity in properties possible. This data represents work-in-process testing of a critical laminate for a gimbal structure used for testing inertia guidance systems (Reference 13). The goal of achieving stiffness (E) in the 0° and 90° directions within 5% was accomplished.

Tooling techniques have been employed to allow large surfaces to be replicated very accurately. Recently, a 130-inch (3.3-meter) reflector was fabricated by COI for General Electric as part of the ACTS Program (Reference 14). The RMS of the completed reflector was 2.5 mils. The composite tool used had a RMS of 2.1 mils. Specific techniques for designing dimensionally stable structures were used to fabricate the tool production mold which resulted in an extremely more accurate part.

FIGURE 7. THE ROTATE AND FOLD LAMINATE CONSTRUCTION TECHNIQUE

TABLE 3. CONTRAVES ITATT INNER GIMBAL MATERIAL TESTING

Panel Cure No.	$E_T(0^\circ)$	$E_T(90^\circ)$
1	9.18	9.35
	8.90	9.23
	9.05	-----
	9.06	9.47
	9.47	-----
2	8.71	8.88
	8.74	-----
	8.65	8.97
	8.49	9.07
	8.94	9.18
3	8.90	9.21
	8.93	8.96
4	8.76	9.28
	8.88	9.10
	8.94	9.15

(0°)

$\bar{X} = 8.91$

Range: : 8.49 - 9.47

±5% : 8.46 - 9.35

(90°)

$\bar{X} = 9.16$

Range : 8.88 - 9.47

±5% : 8.70 - 9.62

3. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Dimensional stability has been controlled in structures from thousandths of an inch to millionths of an inch over wide thermal and environmental exposures.

Stable composite structures have been manufactured and tested for dimensional stability employing the techniques described in this paper. The advent of hydrophobic resin systems has initiated a new level of hygrothermal stability heretofore unachieved in unprotected laminate structures. The impact of employing new materials and design approaches has yet to be fully realized, but efforts are underway to explore this new frontier.

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